

TECHNOLOGY IN INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE INTEGRATED LESSON IN PRIMARY EDUCATION.

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Abstract. This article describes the content and importance of educational technologies in the development of the intellectual potential of students in the educational system. Information about the educational technologies that can be used in the course of the lesson, their main goals and tasks, and their effectiveness is highlighted.

Key words: Integration in education, educational theory, technology, pedagogical technology, educational technology.

ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ИНТЕГРИРОВАННОГО УРОКА В НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЕ.

Аннотация. В данной статье описывается содержание и значение образовательных технологий в развитии интеллектуального потенциала учащихся в системе образования. Освещается информация об образовательных технологиях, которые могут быть использованы в ходе урока, их основных целях и задачах, а также их эффективности.

Ключевые слова: интеграция в образовании, теория образования, технология, педагогическая технология, образовательная технология.

One of the important ideas of today is the need for education to develop in harmony with the progress of modern science and technology. After all, as the President of our Republic Sh.M. Mirziyoyev stated: - «Today we are moving to the path of innovative development aimed at radically renewing all spheres of state and community life. It's not for nothing, of course. Because who wins in today's fast-paced world? The country that relies on a new idea, a new idea, and innovation will win.»

That is why the importance of effective use of integration in the development of education is becoming an important task. Integration in education is not only the development of the child's personality, but also the process of establishing connections between parts of a certain educational system to form a holistic view of the world, aimed at self-development.

In order to connect subjects with each other in schools, to search for new pedagogical solutions, to have an effective and reasonable influence on students, directions that develop the scientific and creative potential of pedagogical teams are gaining great importance. The term «integration» means unity based on the concepts of «combination», «connection», «collection», and is also used in several senses in educational technologies. From a pedagogical point of view, we can consider integration as a mechanism that ensures that the individual level of thinking is determined by the concepts of the level of development of the general mind. This concept reflects the basic conditions for the formation of any system.

In the theory and practice of education, a lot of scientific research has been conducted to give the educational process a technological character. In particular, the idea of technologicalization of education is not new for today. Several centuries ago, the Czech

pedagogue Jan Amos Comenius put forward the idea of technological education. He encouraged education to be «technical», that is, everything, whatever is taught, should be successful. He called the educational process, which leads to the result, «didactic machine». For such a didactic machine, he mentioned in his work that it is important to find clearly set goals, to achieve these goals, clearly adapted tools, how to use these tools, and clear rules.

As we mentioned above, we can see the wide use of terms such as «technology», «pedagogical technology», «educational technology» and «teaching technology» in science and practice. At the same time, there are different types of reading in their understanding. First of all, in order to give a clear expression, to understand what unites them, what separates them, it is necessary to define the concepts of «technology» and its origins: «technological process», «technological action», «technological map», «technological order». If we talk about the term technology, technology means the Greek word «techne» - skill, art, «logos» means concept, teaching, and it is understood that certain processes are organized at a high level of skill and art. The use of technologies to improve the effectiveness of integrated lessons in primary education ensures the organization of this process at a high level of skill and art.

So, educational technology is the general content of the process of achieving the educational goal, that is, the step-by-step implementation of the planned educational process on the basis of a comprehensive system, the development of a specific system of methods, methods and tools in order to achieve a specific goal. means their effective, efficient use and high-level management of the educational process.

We observe that new methods and tools are rapidly being implemented in the educational process to increase the effectiveness of the lesson in primary education. However, instead of some educational forms and active methods, indivisible educational technologies are necessary. However, technological design and planning of the educational process can only be done by a teacher who has technological knowledge, skills and qualifications.

The system of technological knowledge consists of the following organizations:

- a) the conceptual part - a way to learn more complex categories and rules of technology;
- b) an understanding of the component and moving structure of educational technology - the basis for predicting and designing the educational process;
- c) conceptual foundations of educational technologies - any educational technology is based on the pedagogical idea expressed in the achievements of pedagogical and psychological sciences;
- d) setting the goal - if the pedagogical tasks are defined and the final results of the educational activity are unambiguously expressed, if the starting conditions are known, the educational process can be planned;
- e) educational model - a set of acceptable ways (methods and forms) and tools - a guarantee of achieving the expected results in terms of existing conditions and changing the initial state of the object at the specified time;
- f) a set of ways and means of management: forecasting, design, planning, organization, control and evaluation, as well as continuous and regular monitoring of the educational process in order to receive a management conclusion on rapid change - monitoring.

In order to improve the effectiveness of integrated lessons in primary education, before starting to study the basis of technological education, it is necessary to pay attention to the following tips and recommendations:

- The rules expressed on the basis of technology, and with which it is necessary to get acquainted, do not immediately give an explanation, but only show what needs to be done to achieve the expected optimal and effective result.

- Each way and means should be evaluated by the teacher in terms of their visible contribution to achieving the final result they are striving for. While interpreting the acceptability of the rule, it is necessary to pay attention not only to it, but also to the situation or conditions that imply its application.

At the same time, the flow of information is entering our social life with great speed and covering it on a large scale. Receiving information at a rapid pace, analyzing, processing, theoretically summarizing, summarizing and delivering it to the learner, improving the effectiveness of lessons in primary education, integrating them in education is one of the urgent problems facing the system. The application of educational technologies to the process of education and training, to increase the effectiveness of the integrated lesson in primary education, serves to positively solve the above-mentioned current problem.

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